

How to Use RDA Crosswalks to Recommend SDO Markup in Metadata

January 2021

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A REPORT BY THE

World Data System • International Technology Office
Funded under the Alliance (formerly the Canadian New Digital Research Infrastructure
Organization - NDRIO) collaborative agreement number 51387-50326

Cite this report:

Payne, K., & Verhey, C. (2021). How to use RDA crosswalks to recommend SDO markup in metadata. World Data System - International Technology Office.
<https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.4589090>

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How to Use RDA Crosswalks to Recommend SDO Markup in Metadata

One of the outputs from the [RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG](#) was a set of [crosswalks](#) between SDO terms and properties used in metadata standards. This simple set of crosswalks was used to create a suite of [visualizations](#) that allow data managers to investigate how their colleagues have included SDO in their metadata landing pages. The motivation for creating these crosswalks was that it would encourage data managers across domains to utilize SDO in a similar manner, repeating the same types of matches between the SDO terms and similar elements found in different metadata formats, no matter if the metadata format is standard or bespoke. Ultimately, it would assist in supporting best practices in SDO markup.

This document explores one way to use the existing set of crosswalks and visualizations to provide a preliminary set of recommendations for SDO markup for metadata. In this example, we are using a metadata sample obtained in October 2020 from the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center within the Center for International Earth Science Information Network ([SEDAC - CIESIN](#)) at Columbia University.

[SEDAC - CIESIN](#) provided a link to the full FGDC CSDGM (Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata) metadata sample in XML format they currently used in their repository: <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.xml>

1. See if the supplied metadata format is part of the existing set of crosswalks

If your metadata format exists in the list of crosswalks, then you are essentially done; you can visualize the relationship between metadata terms in your standard and SDO terms. In our case, the FGDC CSDGM metadata standard is not currently represented in the crosswalk database, and we will need to crosswalk as many individual terms as we can, based on other crosswalks with similar terms. To do that we need to identify metadata elements to crosswalk from the metadata schema.

2. Identify metadata elements to crosswalk. If you don't already have it, and if you are working from a sample set of metadata, extract the metadata schema.

You may be provided a piece of sample metadata in any number of formats (an HTML landing page, a TXT or JSON file, etc.) and your sample could also have a schema defined in a separate file (for example a DTD or WSDL file).

In our example we have been provided with an XML file and we will extract an [XSD file](#) from the metadata sample. XSD is the schema an XML file adheres to—it defines the structure and elements within an XML file. We will use it to create a target list of elements that we can try to crosswalk to SDO. There are many free online tools available to extract an XSD file from an XML file. XSD is written in XML. In this example we are using the free tool at <https://xmlgrid.net/xml2xsd.html>

The screenshot shows the 'Generate Xml Schema/Xsd From Xml Document' page on XmlGrid.net. The page has a blue header with the site name and navigation links: XML Editor, XML to Excel, Excel to XML, XML to Text, XML to XSD, XSD to XML, and Excel. Below the header, there are four buttons: 'Open File', 'By URL', 'Save', and 'Clear'. A large text box contains instructions: 'Your supplied source data will be displayed in this box. Select the **Open File** or **By URL** command from the menu to load your source data file. After the source data is loaded, click the **Generate Xsd** button to generate the Xml Schema xsd data.' Below this is a 'Generate XSD' button. A second text box contains instructions: 'The generated output data will be displayed in this box. You may save the output by clicking the **Save** command from the menu.'

Either use the “Open File” button to upload your metadata sample or use the “By URL” button to point to the sample metadata online (in our case: <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.xml>)

The top box will show the data source. Click on the “**Generate XSD**” button to extract the schema from the data source. The schema will appear in the bottom box.

The screenshot shows the XmlGrid.net website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo 'XmlGrid.net' and the tagline 'Online XML Editor'. Below the navigation bar, there are several menu items: 'XML Editor', 'XML to Excel', 'Excel to XML', 'XML to Text', 'XML to XSD', 'XSD to XML', and 'Excel'. The main content area is titled 'Generate Xml Schema/Xsd From Xml Document'. It features four buttons: 'Open File', 'By URL', 'Save', and 'Clear'. Below these buttons is a text input field containing the URL 'https://sedac.ciesin.columbia' and a 'Submit' button. A 'TextView' window displays the XML document content, including the 'Data Source' and a tree view of the XML structure. A 'Generate XSD' button is highlighted in yellow. Below this button, a text area shows the generated XSD code, starting with the XML declaration: `<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>`.

By clicking on the “Save” button, the schema will pop up in a new browser window. The top line is the data source (highlighted in yellow below), but the actual XSD file begins with the file type declaration: `<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>`

XmlGrid.net Online XML Editor

XML Editor XML to Excel Excel to XML XML to Text XML to XSD XSD to XML Excel

Generate Xml Schema/Xsd From Xml Document

schema generated from <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.xml>

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<xs:schema xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" elementFormDefault="qualified" attributeFormDefault="unqualified">
  <!-- XML Schema Generated from XML Document on Mon Nov 02 2020 14:22:33 GMT-0800 (Pacific Standard Time) -->
  <!-- with XmlGrid.net Free Online Service http://xmlgrid.net -->
  <xs:element name="metadata">
    <xs:complexType>
      <xs:sequence>
        <xs:element name="idinfo">
          <xs:complexType>
            <xs:sequence>
              <xs:element name="smtype" type="xs:int"/></xs:element>
              <xs:element name="citation">
                <xs:complexType>
                  <xs:sequence>
                    <xs:element name="citeinfo">
                      <xs:complexType>
                        <xs:sequence>
                          <xs:element name="origin" type="xs:string"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="pubdate" type="xs:int"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="pubtime"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="title" type="xs:string"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="edition" type="xs:double"/></xs:element>
                        </xs:sequence>
                      </xs:complexType>
                    </xs:sequence>
                  </xs:complexType>
                </xs:element>
              </xs:sequence>
            </xs:complexType>
          </xs:element>
        </xs:sequence>
      </xs:complexType>
    </xs:element>
  </xs:schema>
```

Beginning with the file declaration (as mentioned above, begins at `<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8">`),

Step 1 – *first screenshot below*: copy the schema

Step 2 – *second screenshot below*: paste it into a good text editor like Notepad++ and save the file as an “.xml - extensible markup language file.”

XmlGrid.net Online XML Editor

XML Editor XML to Excel Excel to XML XML to Text XML to XSD XSD to XML Excel Editor

Generate Xml Schema/Xsd From Xml Document

schema generated from <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.xml>

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<xs:schema xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" elementFormDefault="qualified" attributeFormDefault="unqualified">
  <!-- XML Schema Generated from XML Document on Mon Nov 02 2020 14:22:33 GMT-0800 (Pacific Standard Time) -->
  <!-- with XmlGrid.net Free Online Service http://xmlgrid.net -->
  <xs:element name="metadata">
    <xs:complexType>
      <xs:sequence>
        <xs:element name="idinfo">
          <xs:complexType>
            <xs:sequence>
              <xs:element name="smtype" type="xs:int"/></xs:element>
              <xs:element name="citation">
                <xs:complexType>
                  <xs:sequence>
                    <xs:element name="citeinfo">
                      <xs:complexType>
                        <xs:sequence>
                          <xs:element name="origin" type="xs:string"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="pubdate" type="xs:int"/></xs:element>
                          <xs:element name="pubtime"/></xs:element>
                        </xs:sequence>
                      </xs:complexType>
                    </xs:sequence>
                  </xs:complexType>
                </xs:element>
              </xs:sequence>
            </xs:complexType>
          </xs:element>
        </xs:sequence>
      </xs:complexType>
    </xs:element>
  </xs:schema>
```


Once you save the XML file it will highlight the elements (shown above). We want to identify the metadata elements that can be crosswalked. The elements will be denoted by the element name, like: `<xs:element name="pubdate" type="xs:int"/>`
 We will create a list of element names and crosswalk them to SDO terms.

This XSD document defines a schema for an object or class called "metadata" (`<xs:element name="metadata">`)—this is the one unique root element of the definition file). Within the "metadata" object, it defines several subclasses. By clicking on the + and - signs in the left of your document, you can collapse the information in the sub categories to see the top level classes.

```

1  <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2  <xs:schema xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" elementFormDefault="qualified" attributeFormDefault="unqualified" >
3      <!-- XML Schema Generated from XML Document on Mon Nov 02 2020 14:22:33 GMT-0800 (Pacific
4      <!-- with XmlGrid.net Free Online Service http://xmlgrid.net -->
5      <xs:element name="metadata">
6          <xs:complexType>
7              <xs:sequence>
8                  <xs:element name="idinfo"/>
642                 <xs:element name="dataqual"/>
879                 <xs:element name="spdoinfo"/>
898                 <xs:element name="spref"/>
955                 <xs:element name="eainfo"/>
1019                <xs:element name="distinfo"/>
1169                <xs:element name="metainfo"/>
1240            </xs:sequence>
1241        </xs:complexType>
1242    </xs:element>
1243 </xs:schema>

```

In this case, we can see that it defines elements within 7 sections:

1. Identification Information (idinfo)
2. Data Quality Information (dataqual)
3. Spatial Data Organization Information (spdoinfo)
4. Spatial Reference Information (spref)
5. Entity and Attribute Information (eainfo)
6. Distribution Information (distinfo)
7. Metadata Reference Information (metainfo)

You can inspect each section and see the element names in each one that will be crosswalked to SDO terms. Please note that the terms above were identified using documentation about the metadata standard and matched to their defined element from the xml.

You can also import the XSD file in Excel to see a different view of the schema. Open Excel and browse to the file you downloaded to open. You may get a message saying it is creating a definition file.

elementFormDefault	attributeFormDefault	name	name2	name3	type	maxOccurs	name4	type5	maxOccurs6	name7	type8	maxOccurs9	name10	type11	name12	type13	name14	name15	
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	smtpe	xs:int														
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			origin	xs:string								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			pubdate	xs:int								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			pubtime									
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			title	xs:string								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			edition	xs:double								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			geomform	xs:string								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			serinfo			sername						
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			issue			serinfo						
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			pubinfo			pubplace	xs:string					
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			pubinfo			publish	xs:string					
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			othercit									
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			onlink	xs:string								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			smcInkh	xs:string								
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		origin				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		pubdate				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		pubtime				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		title				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		edition				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		geomform				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		serinfo		sername		
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		issue				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		pubinfo		pubplace		
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		publish				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		onlink				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			lworkcit			citeinfo		onlink				
qualified	unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation			citeinfo			smcIsrcc	xs:string								

When inspecting the elements you can see that the names of elements are reusable in different contexts. For example, within the subclasses of “citation information” there are elements of “title” and “publication date.” If this dataset is part of a larger work citation there are subclasses of “citation information” to document information of the larger work (“lworkcit”), which also utilizes “title” and “publication date.” In the latter case the title refers to the larger work, while in the

former the title refers to the title of the object the metadata is describing (for example the title is the name by which the data set is known).

3. Recognize the Limitations of Crosswalks

There are several issues associated with crosswalks. First of all, as we have seen, the names of metadata elements may be used in different sections of the metadata. Second, the input schema may be very detailed, with many named elements. In contrast, SDO is very generalized, and will not account for all elements in your input file. You should recognize that for these reasons the crosswalks will be imperfect.

More importantly, you should know that you can choose to add the SDO term <name> to mark up the metadata element “Title” within the “citation information” for the data set, *and* you can use the same term (<name>) to mark up the “Title” of larger work citation. If your interest in SDO is to get your data represented in Google Dataset Search ([GDSS](#)), then the spiders will crawl your landing page, find the **first** instance of <name> and index that value. It will ignore subsequent uses of that term (unless it is used as part of a different parent class). For this reason you are well served to make sure your landing page contains the terms you want represented in GDSS first. You should prioritize your markup.

4. Narrow Down Your Target Markup List

This is the tedious part of the task, and it can be helped tremendously by supporting documentation. Using the XSD file, you will step through the list of all named elements in your metadata schema and look for an equivalent SDO term. You can manually add 2 new columns to your XSD file in Excel, one for the parent SDO class and one for the equivalent SDO term. For each named term, use whatever visualization you like and choose the term that seems most like the metadata term in your list. We generally use the open search tag to see all instances of a word. You should know that not all metadata terms will show up in the search. Moreover, you may have to search related words in order to find what you need.

As we mentioned, it is important to prioritize your markup. For this reason we recommend that you first create a crosswalk between mandatory metadata elements and SDO. Classifying terms as being either mandatory or optional is not part of the XSD file, so you will need to look at any guidance documents that exist about your metadata standard to create the list of mandatory terms. You can generally do a simple web search to find documentation for metadata standards. [DataONE also maintains a registry of data and metadata formats](#), and in many cases will have a link to the format documentation. In our case, we can use [guidance from FGDC](#) to identify mandatory terms (highlighted in RED in the table) and check them first. The guidance will help you understand the intent and purpose of the metadata element and any controlled terms used in the element.

attributeFormDefault	name	name2	name3	type	maxOccurs	name4	type5	maxOccurs6	name7	type8	maxOccurs9	name10	type11	name12	type13	name14	name15	SDO Parent	SDO Term
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	smtype	xs:int					origin	xs:string								Creative Work	creator
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						pubdate	xs:int								Creative Work	datePublis
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						pubtime										
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						title	xs:string								Thing	name
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						edition	xs:double									
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						geoform	xs:string									
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						serinfo									sername	
unqualified	metadata	idinfo	citation						serinfo									issue	

Now to reference terms already identified in crosswalked schemas. Not all terms will show up in the SDO crosswalk visualizations, and it will be up to the analyst to find an equivalent. In our example, in the *search table* (below) the mandatory term “origin” (short for “Originator”) is “the name of an organization or individual that developed the data set.” However, because the term “origin” does not appear in any other metadata standard or SDO term in the crosswalk, we will look for similar constructs from other metadata standards. In our case we looked at terms such as different roles in terms like responsible party, publisher or author. Ultimately, we decided “creator” was the closest to the intent of the “origin” term.

Similarly, when we search for the next metadata term “pubdate” there are no results. However, searching for “date” indicates at least 4 other metadata standards that have crosswalked “Publication Date” to the SDO term “datePublished.” Based on this we can add “datePublished” as a recommended SDO markup term in our XSD spreadsheet.

Term	Schema.org crosswalk
dateCreated(M)	dateCreated
Temporal reference: date of publication	datePublished
Temporal reference: date of last modification	dateModified
Publication Date	datePublished
Version Date	dateModified
created	dateCreated
issued / dateAccepted	datePublished

Here are some other useful links:

Dataset landing page:

<https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/set/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11>

Full metadata web page:

<https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/set/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11/metadata>

Full metadata HTML file:

<https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.html>

Full metadata TXT file:

<https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/downloads/metadata/gpw-v4-basic-demographic-characteristics-rev11.txt>